

A FACILE STRATEGY FOR REALIZATION OF MULTI-MODE FLEXIBLE SENSOR CAPABLE OF CONTACT AND CONTACTLESS SENSING

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ABSTRACT

Flexible sensor is of great importance in the fields of manufacture, artificial robot, vehicle and etc. However, the fabrication of multifunctional sensor combined with contact and contactless mode is still a challenge. In this work, a flexible sensor capable of multi-mode sensing was obtained by incorporating Fe₃O₄ nanoparticle/PDMS resin into carbon fiber aerogel. Due to the incorporation of Fe₃O₄ nanoparticle, the as-prepared sensor achieves real-time and precise response not only to strain (contact) but also to magnetism (contactless) sensing in the frequency ranging from 0.1 Hz to 5 Hz. Meanwhile, the content of Fe₃O₄ NP greatly affects the sensitivity of magnetism sensing except strain sensing, which the sensitivity of magnetism sensing reaches 38% under 2000 Oe at the loading of 20% Fe₃O₄ particles. By recording the speed of a running bicycle and running feet, respectively, the magnetism/strain sensor shows great promise in the speed recording through both contact and contactless mode. The current protocol is eco-friendly, facile and thought-provoking for the fabrication of multifunctional sensor.

INTRODUCTION

Flexible contactless sensor is vital to the realization of remote control, especially, in the fields of robots, automobile, aircraft, auto-control, machinery, manufacture, aeronautics and etc.[1-3] So far, a wealthy of physical principles, such as radio[4], light[5], temperature[6], humidity[7], sound[8] and etc., have been applied to achieve contactless sensing. Compared with the aforementioned sensing technologies, magnetic field is the taken to be one of the most promising approach to achieve real-time and precise detecting owing to its excellent compatibility with varied working conditions, and the properties of cost-effectiveness, portability and easy-handling.[9] Nowadays, more than several 10 billion magnetic sensors are produced for various applications, such as speed recording, distance calculation and etc.[10, 11] with the increased requirement over the flexibility, the conventional method is to encapsulate giant magnetoresistive film,[12] , galvanomagnetic film, [13, 14]and Hall Effect film[12, 15] within soft polymer films. However, it is difficult to achieve this target through the aforementioned strategies. Although the incorporation of ferromagnetic powder into polymer matrix provides composite with magnetic response, this type of composite is inappropriate to be used for the fabrication of flexible sensor due to the absence of signal transferring materials.[16] [17] [18] With the increased requirement over the portability and smart design over electronic devices, the realization of multifunctional sensing has long been pursued.[19-21]

Recently, wearable and flexible strain sensor derived from conductive materials, i.e. carbon nanotube, carbon fiber, silver nanowire and etc., has received considerable interests.[22-27] The fundamental mechanism for the strain sensing is that the conducting path built by conducting materials is deformed while applied external force, leading to the increase of relative electrical resistance. After removing the force, the strain will recover to the initial state because of the elasticity of polymer matrix, accompanying with the rebuild of conducting path and recovery of electrical resistance.[12, 28]

Realizing the external force can be induced by applying magnetic field on magnetic materials, in this work, a magnetism and strain sensor was fabricated by incorporating carbon fiber aerogel (CFA) derived from tissue paper into Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles (NP)/PDMS resin. The loading of Fe_3O_4 NP on the sensitivity of magnetism and strain sensing were studied, separately. The performance of magnetic and strain sensor was conducted on a cyclic changed magnetic field and strain, respectively. The contact and contactless mode of sensing were evaluated by recording the speed of a running bicycle and walking foot, respectively.

Figure 1 exhibits the operating principle of the magnetism/strain sensor. It is well known that the electrical resistance of Fe_3O_4 NP/CFA/PDMS composite is determined by the number of conducting path built by carbon nanofiber. The displacement of carbon fiber bring about the breakage of conducting path, resulting in the increase of electrical resistance. Therefore, the relative electrical resistance of composite is determined by the extent of strain. After the removal of external force, the strain gradually restore to zero, the conducting path is rebuilt, and, subsequently, electrical resistance recovers to its initial value, owing to the elasticity of PDMS resin. In a same manner, the strain can be realized by magnetic force after the embedment of Fe_3O_4 NP into PDMS resin. When a magnetic field is applied on Fe_3O_4 NP/CFA/PDMS composite, magnetic force is generated by Fe_3O_4 NP and transferred onto carbon aerogel skeleton, leading to the change of electrical resistance and thus accomplishing magnetism sensing. In addition, the highly stretchable PDMS matrix endows Fe_3O_4 NP/CFA/PDMS composite with excellent wearability and flexibility.

Figure 1: Schematic depiction of the structure of the magnetism/strain sensor responding to the external force and magnetic field.

The sensitivity of sensing capacities over varied frequency of external stimuli is vital to the performance of magnetism/strain sensor for different needs. Therefore, the relative electrical resistance of the composite as a function cyclic strain was characterized. As shown in **Figure 4a**, when a cyclic triangle strain with maximum 10% was applied in a frequency ranging from 0.1 Hz to 5 Hz, the relative electrical resistance exhibits cyclic pattern in the same frequency, indicating the real-time strain sensing. At the frequency of 0.1 Hz, a maximum 27% of relative electrical resistance was obtained. Further increasing the strain frequency leads to the increase of relative electrical resistance. When the frequency increases up to 5 Hz, a maximum of 45 % relative electrical resistance was achieved. In terms of magnetism sensing, as shown in **Figure 4b**, when a cyclic magnetic field with maximum 2000 Oe was applied, the relative electrical resistance shows the same cyclic change. However, in comparison with strain sensing, the sensitivity of magnetism sensing decreases from 38% to 15% as the frequency of magnetic field increases from 0.1 Hz to 5 Hz. The reason attributed to these phenomena is that the toughening effect of polymer under high strain leads to the increased modulus,³¹⁻³³ therefore, higher stress needs to maintain the strain.

Figure 2: Relative electrical resistance of the Fe₃O₄ NP/ CFA/PDMS sensor upon the changed strain (a), magnetic field (b), the cyclic strain (a) and magnetic field (b) under varied frequency, respectively.

Figure 3 Real-time recording of the walking by foot (a) and running by bicycle (b).

The conducting network of carbon fiber aerogel donates the as-prepared sensor with strain sensing, which is widely used to monitor human motions, such as running speed, heartbeat, blood pulse, etc. via physical contact.[29-31] Meanwhile, the inherent property of magnetic field endows the as-prepared sensor with contactless sensing. Here, the property of contact and contactless sensing was verified by recording the speed of walking and running, respectively. **Figure 3** shows the real-time monitor of the walking and running. By counting the average and total number of peaks, the speed and travelled distance can be easily tracked. In addition, the distance-dependence of magnetic field promotes the sensor for the application of distance detection (**Figure 4**).

Figure 4: The function of relative electrical resistance of sensor against the vertical distance between sensor and magnet.

CONCLUSION

A flexible sensor integrated with the properties of magnetism and strain sensing was fabricated by incorporating Fe_3O_4 NP/PDMS resin into carbon aerogel derived from tissue paper. The incorporation of Fe_3O_4 NP endows sensor with magnetism sensing while the carbon aerogel with strain sensing. The

resulting sensor shows excellent properties of magnetism and strain sensing in a wide working frequency ranging from 0.1 Hz to 5 Hz. Study shows the loading of Fe₃O₄ NP is demonstrated to be critical on the performance of magnetism sensing but the strain sensing. A 38% of relative electrical resistance was achieved at the loading of 20% Fe₃O₄ NP. The properties of magnetism and strain sensing were verified by recording the speed of a running bicycle and running feet, respectively. The combination of contact and contactless sensing facilitates the application of magnetism/strain sensor in a wide field. The current approach to fabricate magnetism/strain sensor is proved to be simple and cost-effective. In addition, there is seldom no interference between magnetism and strain sensing, which is inspiring for the bottom-up design of multifunctional sensor not only with the sensing properties of strain and magnetic field, but also with temperature, light, humidity, strain, sound, and ultrasonic.

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